

Biamperometric Determination of some Bivalent Metal Ions

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The determination of bivalent metals like copper(II), zinc(II), cadmium(II) and lead(II) has been reported by many authors^{1,2}. The present communication describes a rapid and sensitive biamperometric technique, using xylenol orange as a titrant, for the determination of copper, zinc, cadmium and lead in their pure samples as well as in their binary mixtures too. Copper was one of the component always present in binary mixtures. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of the mentioned metals in copper alloys, such as brass and gun metal at trace level.

Results and Discussion

The indicator current is due to the electrolytic reduction of metal ions. On addition of the titrant (xylenol orange), it complexes with the metal ions (i.e. bivalent Cu, Zn, Ni, Cd and Pb) hence the current diminished gradually. At the equivalence point and beyond it the indicator current attains a constant value and practically small current flows through the cell. On plotting current by means of B.G. deflection on scale against the volume of titrant (xylenol orange) added, a L-shaped curve was obtained (Fig. 1). The end-point indicates metal to xylenol orange ratio of 1:1 which is in good agreement with the results reported in the literature³.

Simultaneous determination of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}/or Pb^{II}/or Cd^{II}. The test solution (50 ml) containing Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}/or Pb^{II}/or Cd^{II} were placed in the titration cell with a proper amount of the acetate buffer (pH 5.5) at an applied potential of 1.1 V. Copper did not interfere with Cd^{II}/or Pb^{II}/or Zn^{II} at this pH. pH of the mixture was altered by adding

Fig. 1 Determination of zinc (0.65438 mg) present in solution

Fig. 2 Determination of copper (0.6862 mg) and lead (0.5620 mg) present in their binary mixture

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF METAL IONS IN THEIR BINARY MIXTURES

Concn. $\times 10^{-4}M$	Amount of copper (mg)			Concn. $\times 10^{-4}M$	Amount of Pb/or Zn ^{II} /or Cd ^{II} (mg)		
	Taken	Found	Av. error %		Taken	Found	Av. error %
(i) Determination of copper and lead							
2.702 7	0.858 6	0.864 1	+0.64	1.538 5	1.593 9	1.595 5	+0.08
2.432 4	0.772 7	0.775 2	+0.31	1.230 8	1.275 1	1.284 7	+0.75
2.162 2	0.686 9	0.679 9	-1.02	0.923 1	0.956 3	0.953 2	-0.33
1.891 9	0.601 1	0.603 6	+0.43	0.615 4	0.637 6	0.638 2	+0.10
(ii) Determination of copper and zinc							
2.027 1	0.643 9	0.635 4	-1.33	2.400 0	0.784 5	0.784 5	+0.2
2.432 4	0.772 8	0.775 2	+0.31	2.800 0	0.941 5	0.948 0	+0.69
2.702 7	0.858 6	0.857 7	-0.09	3.200 0	1.046 1	1.033 0	-1.25
(iii) Determination of copper and cadmium							
2.702 7	0.858 6	0.864 1	+0.64	1.765 1	0.936 7	0.944 2	+0.8
2.432 4	0.772 8	0.775 2	+0.31	1.320 0	0.749 4	0.741 9	-1.0
2.162 2	0.686 9	0.686 2	-0.09	1.000 0	0.562 0	0.562 0	+0.1
1.891 9	0.601 0	0.597 3	-0.62	0.660 0	0.374 7	0.370 9	-1.0

ammonia solution and adjusted to 8.2. Then, the titration was continued at the same applied potential, copper starts getting chelated with the further addition of the titrant and the current again begins to decrease gradually. At the equivalence point and beyond it the indicator current attain a constant value. On the residual current line, the first end-point corresponds to completion of Zn^{II}/or Cd^{II}/or Pb^{II} determination and the second one to the sum of copper and Zn^{II}/or Cd^{II}/or Pb^{II} determination. The amount of the latter is computed by the difference. The curve has the shape as shown in Fig. 2 and the results are reported in Table 1.

Analysis of the metals in different samples : Several certified samples were analysed after decomposing by the standard method, e.g. brass for copper and zinc, gun metal for copper and lead. The results are presented in the Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF COPPER, ZINC AND LEAD IN STANDARD SAMPLES

Sample (Certified value)	Found %/ (Error %)		
	Cu	Zn	Pb
Brass (Cu = 90%, Zn = 10%)	89	9.9	-
Gun metal (Cu = 85%, Pb = 5% and rest Sn)	(1.12) 84.4 (0.70)	(1.0) -	- 4.9 (2.0)

Experimental

Copper, cadmium, zinc and lead nitrates or sulphates (B.D.H. or Merck analytical grade) were used and dissolved separately in conductivity water and their contents estimated using standard methods⁴. Xylenol orange was dissolved in requisite quantity in conductivity water. Salt solutions were obtained after appropriate dilution of the stock solutions. Conductivity water was used for dilution and preparation of the solutions.

The apparatus and the experimental arrangements used were the same as described earlier².

Procedure : The test solution (50 ml) containing cations (1.00×10^{-4} to $1.00 \times 10^{-5} M$) were placed in the titration cell with the proper amount of acetate buffer (for Cu^{II} pH \approx 5.0 and for Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} or Zn^{II} pH \approx 5.5) or ammonical buffer (for Cu^{II} pH \approx 8.2) at an applied potential of 1.1 V. A stream of N₂ was then passed for 5 min. Xylenol orange solution was added from microburette with stirring when the cations chelated and the current diminished gradually till the equivalence point. When xylenol orange completely complexed with the cations and beyond it the indicator current reached a constant value. On plotting galvanometer deflection against titrant volume a L-shaped curve

NOTE

was obtained. Experiment were repeated several times for concordance.

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